

FROM THE SOUTH: A NEW ALIGNMENT FOR DIGITAL PRESERVATION

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Abstract – The rapid growth of DPC membership in Australasia & Asia-Pacific since 2022 shows the importance of local context for digital preservation. This panel will showcase the work being done by DPC members in Australasia & Asia-Pacific and explore how digital preservation practice is both shaping and being shaped by the evolving social, geographic and cultural contexts around information, knowledge and data management in our region. Speakers on the panel will describe some of the key digital preservation work being undertaken at their institutions with a focus on two main areas: *the challenges of preserving changeable artworks* and *developing appropriate management systems for Indigenous cultural material*.

The Australasia and Asia-Pacific region has a colonial history and a living Indigenous cultural heritage, but digital preservation practices have developed predominantly outside of this context. Therefore, preserving digital material in our region requires new approaches that include engaging with external voices and communities to allow a collaborative re-shaping of practices and space for a diversity of perspectives around the management of knowledge. The work being done by DPC members in our region opens new possibilities for engaging with collections and suggests a new alignment for digital preservation.

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Conference Topics – Haerenga – Journey

I. INTRODUCTION

The Digital Preservation Coalition (DPC) has 27 members in Australasia & Asia-Pacific. They are organizations from the heritage, cultural, commercial and educational sectors with a commitment to preserving their digital content. They also operate in the context of the colonial history of the region and the professional hegemony of standards and practices developed outside of the region. So while the challenges of digital preservation faced by these organizations are often the same as those being addressed elsewhere, there are cultural differences and professional challenges specific to our region that offer opportunities for new approaches and critiques.

Many DPC member organisations in our region are addressing specific digital preservation challenges arising from the local historical, geographic and cultural context. Increasingly in our region the focus of digital preservation is located within a social and cultural space guided by voices and values that come from outside the traditional structures of organisations that hold collections of fixed objects. Instead they are addressing the needs of cultures, communities and artists working to keep their culture and ideas alive and accessible under their own terms. Many of our local member organisations are reassessing the archival impetus to own, store and preserve fixed material heritage and developing systems to redress the historical and current harm this has and continues to cause.

Organisations are working to incorporate new needs and values within the digital preservation journey. This panel will showcase some of the work being done by DPC members in Australasia and Asia-Pacific to listen to and incorporate diverse voices and develop new ways to approach digital preservation in the 21st century.

II. BACKGROUND

In recent policy documents and draft proposals both Australia and Aotearoa New Zealand Governments have addressed the importance of First Nations stories to their nations' culture. [1][2] In response and alongside other protocols, government and other groups are increasingly working to adopt practices that incorporate the information and data management needs of Indigenous communities, including in relation to Indigenous Data Sovereignty [3] and Indigenous Cultural Intellectual Property, into their organizational practice. The DPC and member organisations are responding to the challenges of decolonizing archives as recognized in the Tandanya Adelaide Declaration of 2019 [4]. In particular, the recognition that Indigenous social authority must participate as a collaborator and co-author in record keeping has led to the increasing involvement of communities and to incorporation of their needs and requirements for the appropriate management of Indigenous material held in digital form into institutional practice.

A lesson from the Tandanya Adelaide Declaration is that those holding information need to recognize 'the dynamic and constantly changing relationships across creators, contexts and carriers of information' and to build this into the systems and processes in their organizations. This is leading to changes in digital preservation methods. The need for Indigenous involvement in decision making within digital collections and an understanding that digital information is not static but a 'matrix of diverse living relationships' [4] is leading to the adoption of new workflows and processes. Responsibility for information management can be seen as existing outside of the institutions traditionally charged with it and these relationships require new ways of thinking about digital preservation and the social and cultural impact of information, collections and preservation.

III. PANEL MEMBERS

Moderator: Robin Wright, Head Australasia & Asia-Pacific, Digital Preservation Coalition

Panel members:

Mar Cruz, Conservator (Digital and Time-Based Media Collection), Heritage Conservation Centre, Singapore.

Joanna Fleming, Digital Preservation Manager, Art Gallery of New South Wales

Katrina Hawira, Lead Advisor Mātauranga Māori, Ngā Taonga Sound & Vision, Aotearoa New Zealand.

Elizabeth Long, Assistant Director, Digital Archiving Analyst, National Archives of Australia.

Nicole Lockwood, Assistant Director (A/g) Aboriginal and Torres Strait Islander Engagement, National Archives of Australia.

IV. CONCLUSION

Members of the DPC in Australasia & Asia-Pacific are taking practical steps to implement new ways of thinking about digital preservation by engaging with other voices including artists and Indigenous communities. Making space for understanding the complex relationships between different perspectives and 'critiquing the politics of knowledge production' [5] as part of managing, transmitting and caring for knowledge and culture is an important step towards effective and appropriate digital preservation for communities in all parts of the world into the future.

REFERENCES

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- [4] International Council on Archives Expert Matters Indigenous Group, “Tandanya Adelaide Declaration” https://www.ica.org/app/uploads/2024/01/tandanya_a_delaide_declaration_eng.pdf.
- [5] K. Thorpe, “Indigenous records: connecting, critiquing and diversifying collections”, Archives & Manuscripts: Vol 42 No 2 (2014): Special Issue: Reinventing Archival Methods, doi: <https://doi.org/10.1080/01576895.2014.911692>.

AUTHOR BIOGRAPHY

Robin Wright is the Head Australasia & Asia-Pacific for the DPC. She is a copyright lawyer interested in the intersection of copyright and digital technologies in cultural institutions and tertiary education. Robin has worked in libraries and legal services in the Australian university sector and was previously a Research Fellow at the Centre for Media and Communications Law at Melbourne Law school. She has managed several digital research projects in the GLAM sector. Robin is a Barrister and Solicitor of the Supreme Court of Victoria, is on the board of the Australian Digital Alliance and is Co-Lead of Creative Commons Australia.

